

Analysis of STATCOM Controlled PMSG Based on Shore Wind Farm and Off Shore Wind Farm for Dynamic Stability Improvement

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ABSTRACT: This paper deals with the development of a Mat lab-simulink model of a new proposed scheme for grid connected off shore wind farm (OWF) and marine current farm (MCF) on a static synchronous compensator (STATCOM). The purpose of this simulation Model to getting better damping enhancement and voltage control. An equivalent Doubly fed Induction Generator is used here to operate the Off shore wind farm while an equivalent Permanent magnet Synchronous Generator is used to operate the marine current farm. The PMSG is used to guide for an equivalent marine current turbine and the DFIG is used to guide for an equivalent Wind turbine. To design a damping controller for this proposed scheme model control theory is used here for getting the effective characteristics. The STATCOM controller plays an important role here. A frequency-domain approach based on a linearized system model using Eigen value techniques and a time-domain scheme based on a nonlinear system model subject to various disturbances are both employed to simulate the effectiveness of the proposed control scheme. It can be concluded from the simulated results that the proposed STATCOM joined with the designed damping controller is very effective to Balance the studied system under disturbance conditions. The proposed scheme of this AC bus system can easily control the voltage fluctuations.

Keywords: PMSG, Dynamic stability, doubly fed Induction Generator, marine-current farm, offshore wind farm, FACTS Controllers, Eigen values.

I.INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, Wind Energy Conversion System (WECS) has grown dramatically. Variable-speed wind Turbines (VSWTs) attract considerable interest around the world, which is one of the solutions with the highest potential to reduce wind energy cost. The VSWT systems are usually based on doubly fed induction generators (DFIGs) or permanent magnet synchronous generators (PMSGs). Basically wind farm consists of many wind turbines that are connected with each other to produce small amount of electrical power that becomes powerful after connecting with the transformer. Areas that consists of the number of wind turbines for the sake of power generation from wind and are connected with each other in the different way is called wind farm. Basically wind farm consists of many wind turbines that are connected with each other to produce small amount of electric power. Different strategies are used to build the wind farms in different locations or area. Generators driven by marine-current turbine (MCT) combined with offshore generators driven by wind turbine (WT) will become a novel scheme for energy production in the future. Since oceans cover more than 70% surface of the earth, a hybrid power generation system containing both offshore wind farm (OWF) and marine-current farm (MCF) can be extensively developed at the specific locations of the world in the future. One of the simple methods of running an OWF is to connect the output terminals of several DFIGs together and then connect to a power grid through an offshore step-up transformer and undersea cables. To run an MCF may use several Permanent Magnets synchronous generators (PMSGs) connected directly to the power grid through an offshore step-up transformer and undersea cables.

This paper is organized as below. The configuration and the employed models for the studied integrated OWF and MCF with STATCOM are introduced first[1]. Then, the design procedure and design results for the PID damping controller of the proposed STATCOM using pole-placement technique are depicted. Both steady-state operation points under various wind speeds and marine-current speeds and the comparative dynamic responses of the studied system with the designed PID damping controller under different operating conditions can be elaborately done here. Finally,